

Time Management and Administrative Effectiveness Among Secondary School Principals in Ekiti State

AUTHOR(S): AKINYEMI, TOLULOPE FRANCISCA
AND
PROF. AJAYI, ISAAC ABIODUN (PHD)

Abstract

Some of the secondary school principals in Nigeria appear not to be administratively effective on their job. The extent to which their time management could be responsible for this has not been well established in the literature. This study therefore examined the principals' time management and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population of this study consisted of all principals in 203 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample consisted of 30 principals and 600 teachers who were selected using multistage sampling procedure. Two self-designed research instruments tagged Principals' Time Management Questionnaire (PTMQ) and Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (AEQ) were used to collect relevant data for the study. The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by experts in Educational Management and Tests and Measurements. The reliability of the instruments was established using test re-test method which yielded co-efficient values of 0.91 for PTMQ and 0.72 for AEQ. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study revealed that the levels of time management of secondary school principals were moderate. It was also found out that there was significant relationship between each of the components of principals' time management (delegation of duties and scheduling

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contacts) and administrative effectiveness. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that principals should do more in managing time in the areas of delegation of duties and scheduling contacts in order to improve their administrative effectiveness.

Keywords: Time Management, Administrative Effectiveness, Principals,

About Author

Author(s): **AKINYEMI, Tolulope Francisca**

Zenith Bank PLC.

Ekiti State University Branch, Ado – Ekiti, Nigeria.

And

Prof. AJAYI, Isaac Abiodun (PhD)

Department of Educational Management,

Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti, Nigeria.

Introduction

Administrative effectiveness is the progressive response to administrative efforts and activities with the purpose to achieve stated goal. The administrative performance in making decision, delegation of duties to subordinates, and setting good examples and inspiring the teachers and students alike in an effort to generate a conducive working atmosphere to achieve school goal and objective seem to enhance subordinate performance for school success. Nevertheless, administrative effectiveness of secondary school principal had been observed by Mgbodile (2004), as a factor inhibiting accomplishment of goals in secondary schools.

The researcher observed that some secondary schools are lacking good administration and thus administrative ineffectiveness can easily be observed. Most school administrators seem to face problems in meeting deadlines and curriculum targets. The principal is the chief administrator of the secondary level of education who should always discharge his or her duties timely for general effective administration. It seems that the main reason some school administrators face challenges in meeting deadlines and curriculum goals is poor time management.

Time is a valuable and irreversible abstract resource obtainable for human development. Whatever accomplishments and natural growth of man may be, they are attained with time. It is imperative to every individual, organization and the society at large thus, must be effectively managed. Time is one of the resources that an administrator needs to achieve proficiently in order to attain organizational goals (Khan, Khan, Din & Khan, 2016). The administrator of the school who directs the activities of staffers and students must be able to manage his time very well in order to achieve the aims and objectives of the school.

Nonetheless, what makes time different from other resources used in an organization is that it cannot be accrued or stockpiled like machines and raw materials replaced like a man. Time is irreversible. All it involves is its actual management for organizational success. Time management is very important for everyone. It is the ability to create and follow a schedule, meet deadlines, prioritize and reduce interferences and irrelevant tasks. It comprises managing time wisely so that tasks and projects can be done effectively and efficiently.

As posited by Akomolafe (2005) that time management skills are essentially for effective people.

It has been perceived that the most common difficulties faced by some principals of secondary schools in Nigeria and Ekiti State in particular are their failure to organize and plan their work properly. It is not rare to see principals having standing meetings with members of staff every day after morning prayers. This tends to waste the teachers' time in going for the first periods. These principals also waste their own valuable time as there are some other important issues waiting for them in their offices.

The researcher also observed that some principals attend to issues that should have been handled after their corporate hours. Such issues include needless personal phone calls, wasting much time with drop-in visitors, involving in routines and details that should have been delegated. Experience has also shown that some principals of secondary schools delight pleasure in visiting members of the Parents-Teachers Association (PTA) executive when they supposed to be in the school attending to matters that bother on the school's success. The situations explained above appear to make principals of schools unproductive in their time usage to achieve the aims of the schools.

Considering the implication of principals' time management and its useful effects on administrative effectiveness in schools, this study's intent was to investigate specifically some selected principals' time management variables such delegation of duties and scheduling contacts as a correlate of administrative effectiveness.

Duty delegation includes delegation of tasks to subordinates based on the principle: 'right person for the right job'. Delegation of duties is the act of sharing obtainable functions in the school by the principal to the members of the staff according to their skills and capabilities towards achieving the aims and objectives of the school (Paseda, 2009). In school system, there are many functions that can be deputised to both teaching and non-teaching staff.

Delegation of duties or responsibilities is a significant aspect of attaining time management in the school system. In the school system, delegation of function is a tool in the hands of the principals as the executive head in staff personnel administration. No matter how large the school is, whether big or small, the principal cannot perform all the functions alone, he needs to delegate functions to his staffers for effective time management and school administration.

However, it was observed by the researcher that some school principals prefer to run a 'one man show' administration so as to take all the credit. This category of school principals prefer to carry out administrative tasks without involving staffers nor delegating such duties to competent staffers. Due to time management, it was observed by the researcher that these principals in most cases are usually unable to finish all these responsibilities which directly affect administrative effectiveness in most schools. There are cases where the school principal performs the bursar's duty, and sometimes the duties of the vice-principal. Instead of delegating such duties to the proper person, they prefer to carry out such duties by themselves due to reasons best known to them thereby abandoning their essential duties thus affecting administrative effectiveness.

Scheduling contacts includes being clear about a schedule time, i.e. a start time and a finish time. A good time management technique is to always schedule events and try to stick to them according to the diary, planner chart or calendar in accomplishing educational aims and objectives. Scheduling contacts involve scheduling events, concentrating on a single task at a time, finishing one task before going to another, regularly monitoring time usage, planning schedules to save time and spending most time on profitable activities (Omenu, 2015).

It appears that some secondary school principals allow some school and personal activities to affect each other as they fail to schedule these events and monitor their time usage. It was observed by the researcher that principals in secondary schools focus on many tasks at a time since they failed to delegate these tasks to proficient staffer. In order to finish all these tasks, they do not finish one task before going to another task which harmfully affects administrative effectiveness. Based on the foregoing, this study intends to investigate principals' time management as a correlate of administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

The study therefore examined time management and administrative effectiveness among secondary school principals in Ekiti State. The study specifically examined:

- i. the level of principals' time management in secondary schools;
- ii. the relationship between principals' time management and administrative effectiveness;

- iii. the relationship between delegation of duties and principal administrative effectiveness; and
- iv. the relationship between scheduling contacts and principal administrative effectiveness.

Research Question

This research question will be raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of principals' time management in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' time management and administrative effectiveness in Ekiti State.
2. There is no significant relationship between delegation of duties and principal administrative effectiveness.
3. There is no significant relationship between scheduling contacts and principal administrative effectiveness.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population of this study consisted of all 203 principals in 203 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The secondary schools were located in all the 16 Local Government Areas in the three Senatorial Districts in Ekiti State which are Ekiti North, Ekiti Central and Ekiti South Senatorial Districts. The sample for the study consisted of 30 principals from 30 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

Two self-designed research instruments tagged "Principals' Time Management Questionnaire (PTMQ)" and "Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (AEQ)" were used to collect relevant data for the study. The two instruments (PTMQ and AEQ) were of two sections. Section A of PTMQ sought for bio – data information of the respondents while section B consisted of 28 items. Section A of AEQ also sought for bio – data information of the respondents while Section B consisted of 26 items to assess administrative effectiveness. Likert 4 point rating scale of preference was used for both instruments as follows: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Strongly Agree was scored 4 points, Agree was scored 3 points, and Disagree was scored 2 points while Strongly Disagree was scored 1 point.

The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by Educational Management experts and experts in Test and Measurements. The instruments were said to have facial relevance and concerned with the subject matter, they claimed to measure. The reliability of the instruments PTMQ and AEQ was determined through the test-retest method in four secondary schools outside the sampled area. A co-efficient value of 0.91 was obtained for PTMQ while 0.72 was obtained for AEQ. Both co-efficient values obtained were considered statistically high to make the instruments reliable. The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages, mean standard deviation and bar chart, while the hypotheses were subjected to inferential statistics of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of principals' time management in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

In analyzing the question, respondents' scores on principals' time management were used. Frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation score were used to illustrate the responses to items 1 – 28 in section B of Principals' Time Management Questionnaire (PTMQ). To determine the level of principals' time management (low, moderate and high), the mean score and standard deviation of the responses were used. The low level of principals' time management was determined by subtracting the standard deviation from the mean score ($88.03 - 4.92 = 83.11$). The moderate level of principals' time management was determined by the mean score (88.03) while the high level of principals' time management was determined by adding the mean score and standard deviation ($88.03 + 4.92 = 92.95$). Therefore, low level of principals' time management starts from 28.00 to 83.11, the moderate level starts from 83.12 to 92.94 and the high level of principals' time management is from 92.95 to 112.00. The level of principals' time management in secondary schools is presented in table 1 and figure i.

Table 1: Level of Principals' Time Management in Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

Levels of principals' time management	No of Respondents	Percent age
Low (28.00 – 83.11)	6	20.00
Moderate (83.12 – 92.94)	16	53.33
High (92.95 – 112.00)	8	26.67
Total	30	100

Table 2 revealed the levels of principals' time management in secondary schools in Ekiti State. The result showed that out of 30 respondents, 6 respondents representing 20.00 percent have low level of time management. Those who have moderate time management were 16 respondents representing 53.33 percent while only 8 respondents representing 26.67 percent have high time management. This showed that the level of principals' time management in secondary schools was moderate. Figure ii further revealed the level of principals' time management.

Figure i: Bar Chart Showing Level of Principals' Time Management in Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between principals' time management and administrative effectiveness in Ekiti State

In testing this hypothesis, data on principals' time management were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of PTMQ (item 1 – 28) in the questionnaire. Data on administrative effectiveness were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of AEQ (item 1 – 26) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between principals' time management and administrative effectiveness

Variables	No of Schools	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	r-tab
Principals' Time Management	30	88.03	4.92	0.868*	0.361
Administrative Effectiveness	30	77.67	3.24		

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed that the r-cal value of 0.868 is greater than r-table (0.361) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between principals' time management and administrative effectiveness in Ekiti State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between delegation of duties and principal administrative effectiveness.

In testing this hypothesis, data on delegation of duties sub-variable of principals' time management were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of PTMQ (item 1 – 14) in the questionnaire. Data on administrative effectiveness were

collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of AEQ (item 1 – 26) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between delegation of duties and principal administrative effectiveness

Variables	No of Schools	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	r-tab
Delegation of Duties	30	22.10	1.37	0.658*	0.361
Administrative Effectiveness	30	77.67	3.24		

*P<0.05

Table 3 showed that the r-cal value of 0.658 is greater than r-table (0.361) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between delegation of duties and principal administrative effectiveness in Ekiti State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between scheduling contacts and principal administrative effectiveness.

In testing this hypothesis, data on scheduling contacts sub-variable of principals' time management were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of PTMQ (item 15 – 28) in the questionnaire. Data on administrative effectiveness were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of AEQ (item 1 – 26) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 4.

Table 4: Relationship between scheduling contacts and principal administrative effectiveness

Variables	No of Schools	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	r-tab
Scheduling Contacts	30	22.17	1.37	0.799*	0.361
Administrative Effectiveness	30	77.67	3.24		

*P<0.05

Table 4 showed that the r-cal value of 0.799 is greater than r-table (0.361) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between scheduling contacts and principal administrative effectiveness in Ekiti State.

Discussion

The study revealed that the level of principal's time management is moderate in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The probable reason for this finding might be because some school principals do not know how to properly manage their time effectively. Time management is not about getting more things done in a day. It is about getting the things that matter most done. Time is that quality of nature which keeps all events from happening at once. No wonder Kalu (2012) concluded that time management increases efficiency and productivity.

The study revealed a significant relationship between principals' time management and administrative effectiveness in Ekiti State. This implies that a principal who manages

time will help to improve administrative effectiveness. The probable reason for this finding could be because of the important role of time management in any educational process. Time management increases productivity, effectiveness and efficiency. This finding is in consonance with findings of Eneanya (2009) and Akinfolarin (2017) who found out that a significant relationship existed between principals' time management and administrative effectiveness. When principals are effective in managing their time, the school will highly benefit from their administrative effectiveness. Therefore, time management is a means of fostering administrative effectiveness.

The study also revealed a significant relationship between delegation of duties and principal administrative effectiveness. The probable reason for this finding could be because delegation of duties will make tasks to be completed before deadline. Delegation to staff members gives the principal the opportunity to perform other administrative duties in the school. Akinfolarin (2017) concluded that some members of your staff may become unhappy if you do not entrust them with some responsibilities which they are eager and ready to carry. This result is consistent with previous findings of other scholars such as Nzekwe (2004), Igwe (2004), Eneanya (2009), Ekpenyong (2016) and Akinfolarin (2017) who all found a positive relationship between delegation of duties and principal administrative effectiveness. The result indicated that principals who delegate duties will administratively perform well in school. It could be inferred that there will be administrative effectiveness if principals delegate school duties.

It was further revealed in this study that there was significant relationship between scheduling contacts and principal administrative effectiveness. The reason for this finding might be because scheduling contacts involve scheduling activities, focusing on a single task at a time, finishing one task before going to another, constantly monitoring use of time, planning appointments to save time and spending most time on profitable activities. This finding supports the contention of Britton and Tesser (2001), Macan (2004), Gordon and Borkan (2014), Adu-Oppong, Agyin-Birikorang, Darko and Aikins (2015) and Omemu (2015) that a significant relationship existed between scheduling contacts and administrative effectiveness. The implication of this finding is that when contact and activities schedules are well done, the more the administration is likely to be effective in the school.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded that principals' time management will determine administrative effectiveness; the more principals manage their time; the more administrative effective they are. It is further concluded that delegation of duties and scheduling contacts will go a long way to improve principal administrative effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Principals should do more in managing time in the areas of delegation of duties and scheduling contacts
2. Efforts should be directed by school principals towards reducing impediments to time management by estimating how much time a task will take to be completed, when it must be completed, and then adjusting events that would interfere with its completion in the appropriate amount of time.
3. Secondary school principals should avoid discrimination on the issue of delegation of duties and accept staff opinions and contribution on delegated matters in order to improve their administrative effectiveness.

4. The school principals should schedule their activities by focusing on a single task at a time and finishing one task before starting another task.

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